

A Model To Select Best Design Pattern And Framework For Creational Design Patterns

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Abstract—Software design is a set of activities to solve a software problem. For a high-quality software design the use of software design patterns are needed. Design patterns are documented way to solve a recursive software design problem. Implementation of design patterns refers to as framework for the recursive design problems. Design patterns and frameworks provide high quality software with more reusability, maintainability and extensibility. Due to the large number of design patterns they are categorized as creational, behavioral and structural design patterns even each category has many available design patterns. So, to select an appropriate design pattern is a challenging task. To overcome this problem, this paper gives an overview of the introduction of design patterns and frameworks and focuses on different existing design patterns in the category of creational design patterns. After a detail study of existing literature, the problem of pattern selection from large space of existing patterns, is identified. In order to solve this problem this paper describes a model to select the best design pattern from existing creational design patterns.

Keywords—*Software, Software Design, Quality, Design Pattern, Framework, Software designer, Object Oriented Design Pattern Metrics, SDLC, Open and Close principle*

I. INTRODUCTION

This paper, A model to select the best design pattern and framework for creational design patterns, provides an overview of existing software design patterns and frameworks in creational category to select

the best pattern for specific design problem. Software quality assurance is an umbrella activity, but it becomes more important at the time of software design [1]. The software design is the most sensitive phase of software development life cycle (SDLC) because software design specifies the layout and architectural view of the software. According to Pressman software design encompasses the set of principles, concepts, and practices that lead to the development of high-quality system or product [2]. The software design is based on some principles, criteria and techniques to reduce the complexity of software development [2]. The major principal of software design is abstraction that can be achieved by subsystems, layers, tree structures, encapsulation and information hiding [2]. A good software design satisfies the criteria of completeness, plausible, homogenous, focused with low coupling and high cohesion. So, a good software designer adopts techniques e.g. separation of interface and implementation, usage of open and close principal, function driven, or object driven. The most common technique is open and close principle (OCP) that depicts that software is open for extensions but closed for modifications [3]. OCP is about that the source code of the software is frozen and it should not be re-open when some extension of modification is required but system design is open for the extensions and modifications. Here the need of design patterns arises in an object-oriented paradigm but with few variations these patterns can be applied in any paradigm.

Design patterns are known best practices to solve a recursive design problem. They are more logical in nature. When we apply these logics of design patterns in any programming

language, we get design frameworks. Software design patterns and frameworks improve software quality with more reusability, extensibility and easy maintainability. Design pattern and framework saves time to develop a software with assurance of best design practices involvement. Moreover, they provide a common vocabulary among software developers and helpful in adaptability [4]. Software design patterns are more generic, but framework is specific to a domain and provide functionality. Although frameworks are not independent software application, but new applications can be developed with the help of frameworks.

Design patterns are characterized as “a three-part rule which expresses a relation between a certain context, a problem, and a solution [2]. Shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Design Pattern (A three-part rule)

Nowadays results or consequences of using design pattern and framework is also an essential part.

Existing design patterns are large in number. So, to organize the design patterns space they are categorized based on two criteria.

As shown in Figure 2. one criterion is pattern’s purpose as creational, behavioral and structural design patterns [5]. Creational design patterns abstract the instantiation process, or the underlying software is free from the issues of object creation and representation. Factory Pattern, Singleton Pattern, Prototype, Builder design patterns etc. are examples of creational design patterns. Structural design patterns related to how classes and objects are composed to form larger structures of a system. Adapter or wrapper, Façade, composite design

pattern, Flyweight, Proxy or surrogate design patterns, etc. are example of structural design patterns. Behavioral design patterns are more about how communication take place between objects. Iterator design pattern, Observer or Public, Subscribe, template method, memento, command, architectural etc. are behavioral design patterns. The other criterion to categorize the design pattern is the scope which specifies whether the pattern is applied on class or on the object. Class patterns deal with the relationship among classes and object patterns deal with the objects [5].

Figure 2. Classification of Design Patterns

The selection of good design pattern and framework becomes very challenging in the presence of large design patterns space. In order to limit the scope of this paper we have chosen the creational design patterns only and molded the best pattern selection

according to the problem context. Following are the famous existing creational design patterns:

- Factory pattern is used to define an interface for the creation of an object and subclass decides which class will instantiate the object according to client request [5].
- Singleton pattern ensures that there is only one instance of a class and provides a global point to access it [5].
- Prototype method specify the kinds of objects to create using a prototypical instance and create a new object by copying this object [5].
- Builder pattern separates the construction of a complex object from its representation so that the same construction process can create different representations [5].

Creational design patterns and framework need special care and attention, which requires to adopt an appropriate development process. Design patterns high light those portions of software that can be reused by delegation and dynamic binding techniques of object-oriented paradigm [6]. From large design patterns the selection of best becomes a grate problem for the software designers.

In this paper, a model to select the best design pattern is defined by comparing different creational design patterns, their relationships and applications.

The organization of the paper is as follows: Section II, describes the background by providing the in-depth literature review. Research problem discussed in Section III. Section IV presents proposed solution and result. The paper concludes with section V.

II. BACKGROUND

In this section, I discuss related work that has been done in the field of selection appropriate design patterns and frameworks

for the related context. I conducted a detailed survey analysis to find the gap and gather the knowledge in one place so the reader of the paper can find attraction in selection of best design pattern and framework along with the knowledge of design patterns, creational design patterns, advantages and disadvantages of famous design patterns along with the applications of creational design patterns.

Ralph et al. (1994) describe the idea of architecture in software design [5]. They discuss the most common 23 design patterns. They are also known as the gang of four. They describe creational, structural and behavioral patterns by type. In creational category, they discuss abstract factory pattern, builder pattern, factory method, prototype pattern. In structural category they discuss adapter, bridge, composite, decorator, facade, fly weight, proxy design patterns. In behavioral category, they discuss chain of responsibility, command, interpreter, iterator, mediator, memento, observer, state, strategy, template method, visitor design patterns [5].

Ampatzoglou et al. (2012) discuss a methodology to assess the impact of design patterns on software quality by complete overview of design principles and techniques and how they help in software quality assurance. Their proposed methodology is about comparing different design patterns and give a canonical solution to design patterns [1].

Bertrand(1997) focuses on the software quality assurance factors of correctness, extensibility and reusability by using design methodologies. He starts with abstract data types and then proceeds towards main object-oriented technologies of classes, objects, inheritance, genericity to define different design methodologies [3].

Marshall(1996) describes advantages and disadvantages of adopting and applying, design patterns in the real world. According to him design patterns are valuable tools for the software professionals, design patterns

coordinate all community and process, design patterns let management reward self-directed designer, but the disadvantage of design pattern is the difficulty of understanding them [4].

T. H. Ng et al. (2006) describe the relation of open and close principle and design pattern. They propose OCP as a base toward effective deployment of design patterns for software extension. They conducted an experiment involving 98 software engineering students and concluded that design patterns are basically base on open and close principle.[6]

Khaer et al. (2007) propose a simple and quantitative approach for the analysis of software systems for measurement of design quality. Their comparison of design patterns with object-oriented metrics, visualization, anti-pattern approaches and fault prunes provide a batter approach to estimate the good quality software [8].

Nahla H. Barakat (2019) describes a Framework for integrating software design patterns with game design framework. She emphasizes on the experience of the designer to select the appropriate design patterns for the complex and hard systems. As for some anti patterns the use of patterns can increase complexity and system become more harder to maintain. She integrated some creational and behavioral design patterns to develop a design framework for the game's development [9].

Shahid H. et al. (2019) discuss the automated framework for classification and selection of software design patterns by focusing on the weak points of existing approaches e.g. unified modeling language, ontology, text categorization. They propose that some issues like time and effort for formal specification of design patterns, system context awareness and lack of knowledge should be kept in mind for the selection of design pattern. They propose a three phased method for the designers to choose the best pattern [10].

Shahid H. et al. (2017) describe a text categorization-based approach to select and categorize the design pattern. They focus that

the existing techniques to select design pattern have limitations of lack sample size of patterns, multi class problem and semi-formal specifications. So, they propose a technique based on fuzzy c-means technique which groups together the more related design patterns and choose the best pattern. They also propose an evaluation model to find the effectiveness of the proposed approach [11].

III. RESEARCH PROBLEM

After the detailed review of the related work, it is observed that most of the papers are about design patterns and frame works basic knowledge[2][3][4][7], their effects on software quality[1][8], categorization and selection[5][6][9][10][11] but no one pay attention towards the model or criteria to select the best design pattern and framework from the creational design patterns. In existing approaches there is no criteria or model to select the creational design patterns and frameworks. Moreover, the large number of design patterns and frameworks make it difficult for the designer to select the best one. So, there should be some criteria or model to select the best design pattern according to the scenario.

What are the criteria to select the best creational design pattern and framework?

It is very important to select the best design pattern and framework for a problem. It helps the designers to save the time and effort for the development of a quality software product. The most suitable design pattern supports open and close principle of software design by providing a good level of abstraction. Creational design patterns and frameworks are important in designing of software because they are related to the creation of objects and gives a flexibility in what is created, by whom it is created and how and when it is created. This paper highlights the problem of selection from available creational design patterns.

IV. SOLUTION

Research question is answered in this section by comparing and analyzing the

knowledge of design patterns and frameworks in [2],[3],[4],[5],[6],[7] with the selection and categorization approaches describe in [9],[10],[11].

Design patterns are language independent design solutions for the recursive design problems. Due to large design patterns space the selection of appropriate design pattern for a specific scenario is very difficult. In order to organize the design patterns space, they are categorized into creational, behavioral and structural design patterns. Creational design patterns are related to the creations of objects and abstract the instantiation process. Design patterns and frameworks are scenario specific and there are countless scenarios exist [1].

To overcome the problem of design pattern selection from a large space, this paper is inspired by the working of [10] and [11] so a model is described to select the best creational design pattern and framework by providing the applications and merits along with demerits of some famous creational design patterns.

According to Shahid H. et al. (2017) a text categorization-based approach is employed to select and categorize the design pattern but the way in which they group together the similar design patterns is based on the main types of the design patterns moreover they discussed all categories of design patterns which has broaden the problem space[11]. In this paper, the scope of the research is limited to the creational design patterns because the independence of object creation, composition and representation has a great effect on software quality, maintenance and reusability. So, in this research each creational design pattern is analyzed carefully.

According to Shahid H. et al (2019) an automatic framework is described to select the design pattern that is based on the context knowledge and awareness of all design patterns they discussed almost 103 design patterns in their experiments [10].In this paper, famous creational design patterns are analyzed with their applications.

All creational design patterns and frameworks are concerned with the way of creating objects. To find the answer of research question, following table shows famous creational design patterns and frameworks along with a model to select the design pattern.

Creational Design Patterns and frameworks	Model to Select Creational Design Patterns and frameworks
Factory Pattern	<p>A factory pattern defines an interface or abstract class for creating an object, but it gives freedom to the subclasses to decide which class to instantiate. It is also known as Virtual constructor.</p> <p>We should select this design pattern when</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a loose coupling is required in class hierarchies. Polymorphism is applied by this method. • a class does not know what sub classes will be required to create. • a class wants that its subclasses specify the objects to be created. • parents' classes choose the creation of objects to its subclasses. • abstraction is required between implementation and client classes through inheritance. • an application is to be portable and it needs to

	<p>encapsulate the platform dependencies.</p> <p>The factory design pattern framework can be in any object oriented programming language and requires an abstract class that is an interface or Creator which is visible to the client, concrete implementation of this interface or concrete creator is solely responsible for instantiation details and object creation of the relevant class from class hierarchy.</p>
Singleton Pattern	<p>Singleton pattern defines a class that has only one instance and provides a global point of access to it. There are two forms of singleton pattern one is early instantiation which creates an instance at load time and other is lazy instantiation which creates an instance when required.</p> <p>We should select this design pattern when</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It is required to save the memory because object is not created on each request. A single instance will be used again and again. • a multi-threaded environment is used in system. • In a data base application where only one object is needed to coordinate the actions across the system.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It is used in logging, caching, thread pools, configuration settings. <p>The singleton design pattern framework can be implemented by a static member, private constructor and a static factory method of a singleton class.</p>
Prototype method	<p>Prototype pattern reuses the already instantiated objects. It makes a copy of an object instead of creating a new object. There can be a shallow or deep copy of an object.</p> <p>We should use this design pattern when</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The classes are instantiated at run time • It is required to save time and resources for object instantiation process • It is required to reduce the complexities of object creation. • We want to keep the number of classes in an application minimum. • The client application is unaware of object creation and representation. <p>The prototype pattern framework requires an interface prototype that contains a method <code>getClone()</code> of prototype</p>

	type. It is best method when we want to save memory and resources.
Builder Pattern	<p>The purpose of builder design pattern is to separate the construction of a complex object from its representation. So, we can construct a complex object with simple object with step by step approach.</p> <p>We should select this design pattern when</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • clear cut separation of object creation and representation is required. • more control required over object creation. • change in internal representation of object required. <p>The builder pattern framework requires a Director class that use a builder interface for building the parts of a complex object. Concrete builder class provides implementation for builder interface.</p>

It is necessary to understand the relationships between creational design patterns for the selection of best design pattern. All these creational design patterns have some relationships. But we have discussed the most commonly used creational design patterns that are shown in Figure3. As Prototype pattern configure the factory dynamically. If we see the abstract factory pattern as a single instance creation, we get the singleton design pattern. Abstract factory pattern is implemented by factory method. Builder design pattern creates objects in composite form of composite design pattern. So, all these design patterns have some relationships.

Figure 3. Creational Design Pattern Relationships

The selection of best design pattern and framework becomes easy with the awareness and knowledge of the famous creational design patterns and framework. The relationship and knowledge about different design patterns can help in choosing the best design pattern and framework.

V. CONCLUSION

Design patterns and frameworks give a documented best practice for the solution of any recursive design problem. There are a lot of design patterns and frameworks available. In order to manage the large space of design patterns, they are categorized as creational, behavioral and structural design patterns.

In this paper, the problem of selection the best design problem is addressed. In order to solve the research problem, we have limited the scope of design patterns and frameworks to the creational design patterns. The famous creational design patterns are factory pattern, builder, prototype and singleton design pattern. Although all design patterns belong to the same category of creational design patterns, but the factory pattern is best where we want to give responsibility of object creation to subclasses, whereas prototype pattern reuses the already created object and builder pattern is suitable for complex process of creating objects and Singleton pattern is suitable where only one instance and a point of global access is required.

It is concluded that although all the creational design patterns fulfil the need of object creation in a better way but it is necessary for the designer to know which

pattern is best for their problem domain. So, a high-quality software can be developed.

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